

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

I am very excited to announce the impact factor for 2017, which is the highest impact factor in the 24-year history of our journal. According to the new 2018 JCR, the impact factor of our journal was substantially improved from 0.696 in 2016 to 1.066 in 2017. The 5 year impact factor is now 0.863. Such a success is only possible because of the excellent reviews and the promotion of our journal by the editorial board, the excellent work of the publishing team and the technical support, the very generous support by the J.UCS consortium, but most importantly by the high quality contributions of the authors. Allow me to thank for all your efforts which resulted in this notable success, and I hope we can keep up this great collaboration in the future.

In the second regular issue of 2018, I am pleased to introduce 6 accepted papers from authors of 10 different countries.

In their collaborative research between Brazil and Chile, Thiago S. Barcelos, Roberto Munoz, Rodolfo Villarroel, Erick Merino, and Ismar F. Silveira report about their finding of an extensive and systematic literature review about computational thinking for math learning. Alfonso Garcia-de-Prado, Guadalupe Ortiz, Juan Boubeta-Puig, and David Corral-Plaza from Spain present in their paper Air4People, an air quality monitoring and context-aware notification system, which submits personalized alerts to citizens based on several types of context, whenever air quality-related health risks are detected for their particular context. Andrea Huszti and Zita Kovács from Hungary present in their work a reductionist proof for sender anonymity of an asymmetric bilinear pairing based mixnet (BILMIX). Waldemar Graniszewski, Jacek Krupski, and Krzysztof Szczypiorski from Poland introduce in their paper a new steganographic method where the covert channel is created within the HTTP protocol header, more specifically in the trailer field 1. In a collaboration between Saudi Arabia, UK and Egypt, Alaa A. Qaffas, Alexandra I. Cristea, and Mohamed A. Mead aim in their paper at a lightweight adaptive e-advertising model, the Layered Adaptive Advertising Integration (LAAI).

In a collaborative work between Belgium and Italy, Yvet Wautelet, Manuel Kolp, and Loris Penserini outline the use and validation of a software analysis and project management framework for iterative software development within the Tropos method.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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